

A Case Study on Natural Gas Price Prediction Using Machine Learning Algorithms

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Abstract — Natural gas (also known as fossil gas) is a hydrocarbon gas mixture that occurs naturally and is mostly composed of methane. It is a clean and efficient fuel that is frequently recommended. Its price fluctuates on a daily basis, based on a variety of factors such as location, demand, and manufacturing, to name a few. In this model, we are using the Machine learning algorithms to help predict the values. We chose Decision-Tree Regression Algorithm in this model. Algorithm based on decision trees belongs to the supervised learning algorithms category. It is suitable for both continuous and intermittent use in addition to category output variables.

Keywords— natural gas, machine learning, multilinear regression, decision tree regression algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

Natural gas prediction is crucial in the business world. The goal of this model is to forecast the spot price of natural gas when the user provides the date as an input. It then forecasts the price of gas on that particular day. Natural gas has been offered as a strategy for increasing energy supply security and lowering pollution levels all around the world. Estimating natural gas prices has turned into a truly valuable device for all market participants in competitive natural gas markets, benefiting a variety of stakeholders. Machine Learning Regression algorithms have rapidly gained popularity as a method for predicting natural gas prices. The main goal here is to forecast Natural Gas Prices based on demand and supply. With a high percent accuracy, Decision Tree Regression is the best and most efficient approach for training the machine out of all the techniques. Because of its great environmental benefits, natural gas, one of the most essential energy supplies, will play a larger role in the future of global energy. Forecasting natural gas costs could aid businesses in expanding their operations. This research looks at how machine learning may be used to anticipate natural gas prices. Best accuracy was achieved using the Decision Tree Regression. The dataset is trained for various methods, and the efficiency of each is tested. Finally, the algorithm with the highest accuracy is completed and considered. The ML Algorithm for Linear Regression predicts the worth of the reliant variable y in view of the worth of the autonomous variable x . As a result, it only evaluates one input, whereas we have three: day, month, and year.

As a result, the ML Algorithm for Linear Regression cannot be applied. Instead, you might utilise the Multiple Linear Regression Algorithm. It predicts the result of a response variable using many explanatory variables. A reliable natural gas price projection model is incredibly beneficial. This data is used by natural gas operators to assess the economics.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Dimitrios Mouchtaris, Emmanouil Sofianos, Periklis Gogas, Theophilos Papadimitriou[1] developed an attempt using machine learning approaches, to forecast the natural gas spot price for the next 1, 3, 5, and 10 days: using SVMs, regression trees, linear regression, and Gaussian process regression.

Moting Su, Zongyi Zhang, Ye Zhu[2] Using conventional machine learning tools, constructed data-driven predictive models for natural gas price forecasting. such as neural networks created artificially, support vector machines (SVM), gradient boosting machines (GBM), and Gaussian process regression in this research. (GPR) For model training, used cross-validation and monthly Henry Hub natural language processing.

Jiarong Mu, Xianfeng Liu, Peiyan Zang[3] developed a natural gas futures price's non-linear and long-term dependence, this paper makes a prediction using the long-term and short-term memory (LSTM) model, which can be extended in time and has a long-term memory function, and effectively solves the gradient explosion problem of traditional neural networks.

Ervin Ceperic, Sasa Zikovic, Vladimir Ceperic[4] developed a short-term Henry Hub spot natural gas price predictions based on the performance of conventional time series models and machine learning methods, notably neural networks (NN) and strategic seasonality-adjusted support vector regression machines, are presented (SSA-SVR). The use of feature selection (FS) methods to generate model inputs and choose model inputs is suggested.

Yuanyuan Tang, Qingmei Wang, Wei Xu[5] examines whether internet search data and news sentiment may help with predicting and compares which can produce better outcomes. The findings of the experiments suggest that both internet search and news sentiment contain additional information that can increase the prediction effect, and that internet search data can produce better predictions.

III. MOTIVATION

Natural gas has been offered as a strategy for increasing energy supply security and lowering pollution levels around the world. Forecasting natural gas prices has become a very

valuable tool for all market participants in competitive natural gas markets, benefiting a variety of stakeholders. Natural Gas Price Prediction is useful for both businessmen and customers in deciding whether or not to invest in a project and in planning purchases when a favorable rate is expected. We can find out the values without having to go to the websites and look for them. We can use the pricing from previous years to estimate a value for the coming years.

IV. METHODOLOGY

The goal of this model is to predict the spot price of natural gas when the user provides the date as an input. It then predicts the price of gas on that particular day. To train and predict an outcome, the supplied model employs a dataset known as the "Training Dataset." The structure obtained is given as follows:

Following are the steps during the implementation:

1. Data Collection: The information was gathered using the Henry Hub Natural Gas Spot Price. Natural gas prices fluctuate from day to day, as they are largely determined by supply and demand. Because of its huge trade volume and

pricing transparency, gas producers rely on the Henry Hub's natural gas spot pricing. The dataset 'data updated.csv' contains dates as well as their related day, month, year, and price.

2. Data Preprocessing: The data is processed or encoded in this stage so that the machine can interpret it. Because the date is broken into day, month, year, and price, our data is numerical. The steps for pre-processing the data are as follows:

a. Importing Libraries: Using packages such as pandas to read a dataset and convert it to a DataFrame, and NumPy to transform DataFrames into arrays and manipulate them.

b. Reading Dataset: The pandas read csv() function reads and stores a csv (comma-separated values) file in a DataFrame. The functions head() and tail() are used to return an integer representation of the number of rows supplied in the parameter.

c. Handling Missing Values: Our dataset has a missing cost esteem, which is supplanted by the dataset's mean cost esteem utilizing the fillna function().

d. Split data into train and test: To split a dataset into train and test datasets, use the method train test split() A total of 20% of the dataset is preserved for testing purposes. The internal random number generator is initialized with random state=0, which determines how data is split into train and test.

3. Data Analysis: Statistical Data Analysis- The pandas describe() function returns a DataFrame that contains statistical data such as count, mean, median, mode, and so on.

Analysis of Visualizations: The Matplotlib module in Python allows you to create static, animated, and interactive visualisations. The seaborn library is used to create an appealing and informative statistics graph using a high-level interface.

4. Training Model: Regression Machine Learning Algorithms must be used to create the model. The ML Algorithm for Linear Regression predicts the value of the dependent variable y based on the value of the independent variable x. As a result, it only evaluates one input, whereas we have three: day, month, and year. As a result, the ML Algorithm for Linear Regression cannot be applied. The Polynomial Regression Algorithm is similar in that there are several inputs and the outcome cannot be described as an nth degree polynomial. Instead, you might utilise the Multiple Linear Regression Algorithm. It predicts the result of a response variable using many explanatory variables. As a result, it forecasts price outcomes based on the day, month, and year. The Decision Tree Regression Algorithm turns out to be an excellent choice. The Decision-Tree Algorithm uses a tree structure to create regression or classification models. It accomplishes this by breaking down a dataset into smaller sections while creating an associated decision tree progressively. Finally, a tree with decision-nodes and leaf-nodes is produced.

5. Evaluation and Testing: Think about accuracy and efficiency as the major goals while discussing Machine Learning testing approach. Multilinear Regression and

Decision Tree Regression are the techniques utilised in the Natural Gas Price Prediction dataset. The dataset is trained for these algorithms, and the efficiency of each is assessed. Finally, the approach with the highest accuracy is finalized and considered. The data and other algorithms are disregarded during training. We now import r2 score from sklearn.metrics to assess the correctness of the Algorithm. For specialised purposes, the metrics module uses functions to estimate prediction error. Classification metrics, Multilabel ranking metrics, Regression metrics, and Clustering metrics are all covered in depth in this section.

6. Saving Model: We employ dictionaries, DataFrames, and other data types to store data sets. You may wish to save them to a file so that you can use them later or email them to someone else. The pickle module does exactly that: it serialises objects such that they may be saved to a file. Then, when needed, it can be loaded into a software again. Pickling is useful for applications that require a certain level of data permanence.

V. BUILD MODEL

Regression Machine Learning Algorithms must be used to create the model. It is possible to apply the Multiple Linear Regression Algorithm. It predicts the result of a response variable using many explanatory variables. As a result, it forecasts price outcomes based on the day, month, and year. It use the formula:

$$y = a_0 + a_1x_1 + a_2x_2 + \dots + a_nx_n$$

xi: a variable that is not dependent on others.

a0: constant ai: each xi's slope coefficient

However, in this case, the algorithm proves to be ineffective.

MULTILINEAR REGRESSION

```
from sklearn.linear_model import LinearRegression
mlr=LinearRegression()
mlr.fit(x_train,y_train)
```

```
y_pred=mlr.predict(x_test)
```

```
from sklearn.metrics import r2_score
accuracy=r2_score(y_test,y_pred)
```

```
accuracy
```

```
0.006791562606343282
```

The accuracy obtained using the Multilinear Regression Algorithm is very low. Therefore we will not use this algorithm. The Decision Tree Regression Algorithm turns

out to be an excellent choice. The Decision-Tree Algorithm uses a tree structure to create regression or classification models. It accomplishes this by breaking down a dataset into smaller sections while creating an associated decision tree progressively.

```
from sklearn.tree import DecisionTreeRegressor
dtr=DecisionTreeRegressor(random_state=3,criterion='mse',max_depth=10)
dtr.fit(x_train,y_train)
```

```
dtrpred=dtr.predict(x_test)
```

```
from sklearn.metrics import r2_score
dtraccuracy=r2_score(y_test,dtrpred)
```

```
dtraccuracy
```

```
0.9756025706718756
```

The accuracy obtained using decision tree regression is more so this algorithm is used for the prediction.

Evaluation of Accuracy: A model must not only forecast properly, but also do so because it is algorithmically correct, rather than by chance. If 99 percent of emails aren't spam, then classifying all emails as not spam has a 99 percent chance of being correct. As a result, you must verify that your model is algorithmically correct. Take the following steps: Verify that the loss lowers after training your model for a few iterations. Without regularisation, train your algorithm. Your model will memorise the training data if it is complex enough, and your training loss will be near to zero. Specific sub-computations of your method should be tested.

VI. RESULT

The result shows that the decision tree regression method has a maximum accuracy of 97 percent based on the above predictions.

	day	month	year	price
count	5563.000000	5563.000000	5563.000000	5563.000000
mean	15.708790	6.483552	2007.633112	4.307914
std	8.740374	3.413840	6.416366	2.206769
min	1.000000	1.000000	1997.000000	1.050000
25%	8.000000	4.000000	2002.000000	2.760000
50%	16.000000	6.000000	2008.000000	3.690000
75%	23.000000	9.000000	2013.000000	5.430000
max	31.000000	12.000000	2020.000000	18.480000

VII. CONCLUSION

In this paper the model is trained to take the user's date as input, check the price against the dataset, we used to train it, and output the anticipated price. It gives an introduction about Natural Gas and Machine Learning. Under Machine Learning, the entire process of accepting inputs, assessing variables, and then predicting the output is based on the Decision Tree Regression algorithm. We aim to include the location as an input and forecast values for it as the price changes depending on the location because this is a basic model that predicts based on dates.

Because this model does not forecast the future, we can include features such as historical performance, natural disasters, and changes in the demand for autos, among others. And make the model capable of predicting the approximate price for future dates so that investments and company can be adequately considered and planned.

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